

Study of the wettability of lignocellulosic and synthetic fabrics for the treatment of brackish water

Alexis, López Borrell.¹, Jaime, Lora García.¹ María-Fernanda, López-Pérez.¹, Salvador C., Cardona Navarrete.¹, Vicent, Fombuena Borrás.²

¹ Instituto de Seguridad Industrial, Radiofísica y Medioambiental (ISIRYM), Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Plaza Ferrándiz y Carbonell, s/n. 03801 Alcoy

² Technological Institute of Materials (ITM), Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Plaza Ferrándiz y Carbonell, s/n. 03801 Alcoy

Today, waste generation is increasing due to the planet's population growth and the generational consumption that goes with it. This is associated with the increase in industrial production and the consumption of available natural resources. Amongst these factors, one sector that is very much affected is the production of fresh water and food. Currently, the demand for drinking water in coastal areas has been met by desalination plants and the large amount of waste from urban areas is managed in urban solid waste treatment plants [1,2].

The aim of this work is to study the behaviour of natural and synthetic commercial fabrics to reduce the volume of brackish water waste, taking advantage of the growth in the production of these fabrics in recent years [3]. The objective is to reduce the volume of waste generated in these activities by using the fabrics to evaporate water. This study will compare natural bamboo (Bam), linen (LPLA), jute (Jut) and wet-laid (WL-WT and WL-T) fabrics with commercial synthetic fabrics of non-woven and woven glass fibre (GF-NW, GF-W), polyester (PES) and aramid (Ara). The liquid absorption capacity (LAC) to distilled water and to a synthetic solution of brackish water will be determined, observing the retention of salts on the samples.

The main results have shown at Figure 1, the synthetic polyester fabric has the highest liquid absorption capacity in distilled water and brackish water with a value of more than 800%. Lignocellulosic fabrics show wettability ranging from 100 to 250% in the case of distilled water. Synthetic fabrics oscillate between 35 to 65% for glass fibres and in the case of aramid it has a value of approximately 139%. By exposing the samples to the dissolution of brackish water and working in different cycles of operation the dispersion of the absorption in the fabrics is stabilised due to the precipitation of the salts on the samples. In this case, all tissues show an increase in the absorption capacity and a lower scattering.

After studying the exposure of the fabrics to the dissolution of the brackish water, it was observed that after 5 cycles of operation, the samples with greater absorption capacity had retained a greater quantity of precipitated salts. The most notable was that of PES with an increase in mass of 17.19% with respect to its initial weight, the results can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 1. LAC of the different samples in distilled water and brackish water in 1 absorption cycle and after 5 cycles. ■ LAC distilled water (%), ■ LAC brackish water 1 cycle (%), ■ LAC brackish water 5 cycles (%)

Figure 2. Increased weight in the samples due to precipitation of salts from the brackish water solution. ■ Salt accumulation (%)

Bibliography

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